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[REDACTED] Labone
Accra – Gha

30th September 2021

The Clerk
Committee on Constitutional Legal & Parliamentary affairs
Office of Parliament
Osu
Accra - Ghana

Dear Sir,

WRITTEN MEMORANDUM ON THE PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL 2021
RE: REQUEST FOR WRITTEN MEMORANDA (DPA/21)

Introduction

My name is S [REDACTED] A [REDACTED], a young Journalist/Radio presenter with [REDACTED], researcher and a law student of the Central University faculty of law. Over the past four years I have explored experiences across diverse areas of advocacy and research on human rights in Ghana. Particularly, I spent four years working under the state-run Justice for All Programme for Remand prisoners. I also had to the privilege to assist in setting up Ghana's first access to justice intervention for convicted prison inmates called the In-Prison Paralegal Project. I was also instrumental in compiling the over seventy reports and factsheets submitted by CSOs/NGOs from Ghana to the UN Human Rights Council in Geneva during the 2017 UN Universal Periodic Review as well as many other significant research works, project management and facilitation services provided to different organizations.

The above mentioned experiences have given me a unique insight into various human rights issues pertaining to key populations in Ghana thereby necessitating my interest in contributing to this important law making process by the house.

General concerns/Critique of the PPSRGFV Bill 2021

“Homosexuality has never been un-African, but rather, just another form of sexuality that had been suppressed for years... it is something we are living with. - Nelson Mandela in Gift Siso Siphon and B Atieno (2009).

The former Secretary General of the United Nations, Mr. Ban Ki-Moon, on the 25 January 2011, at the Human Rights Council in Geneva said the following and I quote;

"We must reject persecution of people because of their sexual orientation or gender identity who may be arrested, detained or executed for being lesbian, gay, bisexual transgender. They may not have popular or political support, but they deserve our support in safeguarding their fundamental human rights. I understand that sexual orientation and gender identity raise sensitive cultural issues. But cultural practice cannot justify any violation of human rights... When our fellow human beings are persecuted because of their sexual orientation or gender identity, we must speak out."

And that is what I am doing today. Speaking out for the many men and women who cannot find their voices to speak out because society has silenced them and made third class citizens as though deserving of none of the rights provided by the constitution that binds us all together and gives us one identity as Ghanaians.

Retention of provisions prohibiting “unnatural carnal knowledge,” failure to proactively address violence and discrimination, and the role of some politicians in inciting homophobia combine to relegate LGBT Ghanaians to what can be described as second-class citizenship.

What does international law say about criminalization?

The United Nations Human Rights Committee has confirmed that laws criminalizing homosexuality violate rights to privacy and non-discrimination in breach of States’ legal obligations under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. Where these laws are enforced, they may also lead to violations of the right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.⁶

Everyone has the right to be free from criminalization and any form of sanction arising directly or indirectly from that person’s actual or perceived sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression or sex characteristics.⁷ States shall repeal criminal and other legal provisions that

prohibit or are, in effect, employed to prohibit consensual sexual activity among people of the same sex who are over the age of consent.⁸

What are the consequences of criminalization?

In addition to violating basic rights, criminalization legitimizes prejudice in society at large and exposes people to hate crimes, police abuse, torture and family violence. Criminalization also has a dire effect on public health, especially on efforts to prevent the spread of HIV. It can, for example, deter some of those most at risk of infection from coming forward for testing and treatment out of fear of being deemed a criminal.

It can also endanger those who work to defend the human rights of LGBTI people by exposing them to attacks and intimidation. Criminalization also fuels discrimination against people who dress or behave in a way that challenges traditional gender norms. There have been many incidents of individuals arrested or attacked based on their clothes, mannerisms and style of speech.

Public Health Concerns

The United Nations Human Rights Council has provided many resources and the opportunity to review the impact of the criminalization of LGBTQ+ persons on the health and well-being of mankind. The recent Update on National HIV&AIDS Response by the Ghana AIDS Commission indicates that about 54,800 of the country's total AIDS population of 346,120 are men sleeping with men (MSMs).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to which Ghana has committed to makes it imperative that no one is left behind. A people-centered, public health and human rights-based approach key to addressing the prevalence of HIV&AIDS among communities. Criminalization will however further compound the issue as LGBTQ+ persons will be afraid to seek treatment thereby putting the whole country at a higher risk.

Increased Prison Populations

Ghana is still struggling with the issue of prison overpopulation and congestion, the weight of which is crippling. Current statistics indicate that the overcrowding rate is hovering way over 52%. The Nsawam medium security Prisons for instance has an authorized capacity of 815 inmates but currently holds over 3400 inmates.

The conditions of our prisons is nothing to write home about. In fact, Ghana's prisons have been described as unfit for humans and already violate inmate's rights to dignity, from the poor feeding conditions to the unsanitary living conditions. One can only imagine the burden the criminalization of LGBT persons will put on the prison system.

Recommendations

In view of the above, I am highly opposed to the ‘Promotion Of Proper Human Sexual Rights And Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021’ and recommend that the Bill is not considered. It is a violation of the constitutional right to privacy and goes against Ghana’s obligations under international law. It is not progressive and portrays Ghana as an intolerant nation especially for a country that has been hailed as the most hospitable in the sub-region.

The House should instead consider inclusivity and focus on Bills that promote tolerance as well as take steps ensure the implementation of the two recommendations Ghana accepted during the review of its human rights status during the last UN Universal Periodic Review in Geneva in 2017.

Submitted by

Yours faithfully,

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